

Youth Perception towards Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan: A Comparative Study of College and University Students

Dr. Arjun Gope

Associate Professor

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Head of the Department, Department of Commerce, Ramthakur College, Tripura

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Abstract: This research paper analyzes the perceptions of youth towards the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan (Self-Reliant India Campaign), with a particular focus on the differences between college and university students. By evaluating their views on various aspects of the initiative, including its awareness, role in strengthening the economy, encouragement of entrepreneurship, reduction of dependency on external players, and government training programs, the study highlights key insights into the effectiveness and reach of the campaign. The finding suggests that both college and university students, in general, have similar views on various aspects of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan. These finding can provide valuable information for policymakers to enhance the outreach and impact of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan.

Keywords: Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan, entrepreneurship, youth, economy, awareness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship plays a vital role in innovation, job creation and economic development. In India, the government has implemented various initiatives to support young people, particularly students, in launching new businesses. The Government takes different initiatives to for creating and providing favorable environment for the entrepreneurs. During the COVID-19 all the countries across the Globe have realized the importance of being self-reliant. At this backdrop Government of India launched Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan (Self Reliant India Campaign) in the 2020 with the objective of fostering self-reliance by reducing dependency on external forces and promoting domestic businesses and entrepreneurship. The initiative aims to encourage local manufacturing, empower youth, and build a resilient economy. As part of this initiative, the government has emphasized the role of youth in achieving self-reliance by providing training programs, financial assistance, and a conducive environment for entrepreneurship.

This research explores the perception of youth towards the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan, with a focus on comparing college and university students' views. The study assesses their awareness of the initiative, its role in strengthening the Indian economy, its potential to encourage entrepreneurship, reduce dependency on external players, and the government's efforts in arranging training programs to boost entrepreneurial activities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

“Atmanirbhar” or “self-reliance” is a new way of thinking about the economic development's mechanisms and outcomes. Economic self-reliance refers to a person's capacity to accumulate and maintain economic resources in excess of their essential requirements. Self-sufficiency is not a new phenomenon in India. According to Saxena (2020), India has achieved partial success and has become self-sufficient in agriculture and food production, with record outputs of cereals, fruits, and vegetables, as well as the highest production of milk in the world. In their Report (2020), the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development stated that in order to address the looming financial crisis or liquidity shortage that developing countries are facing, special financial needs, capital regulation by the IMF, and a new debt relief programme, among other

things, are needed. The Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan has been widely discussed in government reports and academic literature. Studies on entrepreneurship and self-reliance emphasize the importance of youth involvement in national development (Gupta, 2020). Government initiatives like training programs and financial support have been shown to encourage entrepreneurial spirit (Seth & Singh, 2021). However, perceptions regarding these initiatives vary among different groups. In particular, the differences between educational institutions, such as colleges and universities, have not been extensively studied in the context of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan. Understanding these differences is crucial for improving the outreach of the initiative.

However, there is limited research comparing the perceptions of youth from different educational institutions regarding Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan. Understanding how these perceptions differ can provide valuable insights for policymakers to design more effective initiatives targeted at the youth demographic.

Research Objectives

These objectives of the study:

- i. To assess the level of awareness among college and university students about the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan.
- ii. To determine if there are significant differences between college and university students' perceptions regarding the campaign of Atmanirbhar Bharat.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A survey has been conducted with 500 students, consisting of 390 college students and 110 university students from north-east India. Descriptive statistics along with the Kruskal-Wallis test have been run to determine if there are statistically significant differences in the perceptions between college and university students.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This data (Exhibit-1) reflects the perceptions of youth regarding various aspects of Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan. The data collected revealed several key insights into the scheme of Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan.

The data shows that youth have a generally positive perception of the Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan. Awareness of the initiative is high, with around 67% of youth recognizing its objectives. 66.4% youth also support the government's efforts to strengthen the economy and 56.8% reduce dependency on external players. However, perceptions around encouraging entrepreneurship are mixed, with 56% agreeing but a significant number remaining neutral.

While positive sentiments are strong, a notable 27% remain neutral, indicating a need for greater engagement and clearer communication. Additionally, some youth are skeptical, especially regarding the impact on entrepreneurship and dependency reduction.

Exhibit-1: Perception of youth towards Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan

Views	The objective of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan is known (awareness) to the educated youth		The Government under the Atmanirbharat Bharat Abhiyaan takes initiative to strengthen the Indian economy		The Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan is growing into a movement in India to encourage entrepreneurship among youth		Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan will reduce the dependency of the society on the business giants and external players		Govt. frequently arranges short term special training programme for the students to motivate and enhance the entrepreneurial activities	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
SD	22	4.4	33	6.6	28	5.6	35	7.0	38	7.6
D	36	7.2	30	6.0	41	8.2	46	9.2	38	7.6
N	107	21.4	105	21.0	151	30.2	135	27.0	135	27.0
A	185	37.0	206	41.2	168	33.6	197	39.4	168	33.6
SA	150	30.0	126	25.2	112	22.4	87	17.4	121	24.2
	500	100.0	500	100.0	500	100.0	500	100.0	500	100.0

SD= Strongly Disagree; D= Disagree; N= Neither agree nor disagree; A= Agree; Strongly Agree

Source: Author's compilation, using SPSS, from Primary Data (2024)

Overall, the initiative is well-received but could benefit from increased outreach and expanded training programs to solidify its effectiveness.

Exhibit-2 displays the Mean Rank of youths, colleges and universities students, perception towards Ease of Doing Business (EoDB). The college students have a higher mean rank for the cases of (i) Government Support (ii) Taxation system (iii) Licensing and permission, indicating they generally perceive more government support, friendly taxation system and easier Licensing and permission for youth entrepreneurship compared to university students. The gap suggests university students may feel less supported or less confident in for business startups.

The Exhibit-2 presents the mean rank of youth perceptions towards the Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan based on their affiliation with either college or university. However, College students

Exhibit-2: Mean Rank of youths perception towards

Perception Statements	HE Institutions	No of Students	Mean Rank
1. The objective of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan is known (awareness) to the educated youth	College	390	258.42
	University	110	222.43
2. The Government under the Atmanirbharat Bharat Abhiyaan takes initiative to strengthen the Indian economy	College	390	252.11
	University	110	244.79
3. The Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan is growing into a movement in India to encourage entrepreneurship among youth	College	390	256.28
	University	110	230.00
4. Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan will reduce the dependency of the society on the business giants and external players	College	390	250.61
	University	110	250.12
5. Govt. frequently arranges short term special training programme for the students to motivate and enhance the entrepreneurial activities	College	390	250.13
	University	110	251.83

Source: Author's compilation, using SPSS, from Primary Data (2024)

tend to have slightly more positive perceptions of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan in terms of awareness, government initiatives, and entrepreneurship encouragement. The difference in perception between college and university students is not very large, suggesting that both groups recognize the significance of the initiative, but college students generally feel a bit more engaged or informed. Training programs seem to be viewed slightly more favorably by university students.

The Kruskal-Wallis test (Exhibit-3) is used to determine whether there are statistically significant differences between the ranks of groups (in this case, college vs. university students' perceptions). The test statistics provided here for each perception statement help assess whether the difference in perceptions across the groups is statistically significant.

Exhibit-3: Test statistics of Kruskal Wallis Test

	Awareness	Strengthen the Indian economy	Encourage entrepreneurship	Dependency on external players	Training programme
Chi-Square	5.837	.244	3.077	.001	.013
df	1	1	1	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	.016	.621	.079	.974	.910

Source: Author's compilation, using SPSS, from Primary Data (2024)

The Kruskal-Wallis test results indicate no statistically significant differences between college and university students for the cases of government initiatives, and entrepreneurship encouragement, Dependency on external players and Training programme as all the p-values are greater than the 0.05 threshold. However, there is a significant difference in the perception of awareness of the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan between college and university students (p-value = 0.016). This suggests that both groups, in general, have similar views on various aspects of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan, with only marginal differences in case of Encouraging entrepreneurship as the value is close to 0.05 and difference in the case of perception of awareness of the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan.

5. CONCLUSION

The study finds the youth's perceptions regarding the Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan indicating generally a positive response towards the initiative. A significant proportion of youth (67%) are aware of its objectives, and many support its goals to strengthen the Indian economy (66.4%) and reduce dependency on external players (56.8%). However, perceptions regarding the encouragement of entrepreneurship are mixed, with a sizeable portion remaining neutral or uncertain about its effectiveness. The study confirms that there are no statistically significant differences between college and university students' perceptions on most aspects of the initiative, except for the awareness of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan. This finding indicates that college students have a marginally better understanding of the scheme compared to university students, which points to the need for further outreach efforts to bridge this awareness gap. Policymakers and institutions can use these insights to target awareness programs more effectively and ensure that the campaign reaches all segments of the youth population. Additionally, further research could explore the reasons behind the awareness gap and identify strategies to address it.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Gupta, A. (2020). Youth Entrepreneurship and Atmanirbhar Bharat: A Step Towards Self-Reliance. *Journal of Indian Economic Policy*, 10(2), 45-56.
- [2] Seth, S., & Singh, R. (2021). Government Initiatives for Entrepreneurship in India: A Critical Review. *Journal of Business Studies*, 15(4), 125-136.
- [3] Saxena, J. (2020). making farmers self client. *Yojana*, 64 (7), 20-25.
- [4] Thapliyal, J (2020); Gandhi's Goal of Self Reliance Has Its Reflection in Atmanirbhar Bharat; Available at: <https://www.thehawk.in/feature-posts/gandhis-goal-of-self-reliance-has-its-reflection-in-atmanirbhar-bharat-175930>; Accessed on: 29/03/2021
- [5] United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (2011); A Common Future to The Future we Want; Available at: <https://rio20.un.org/resolutions-more?page=1>; Accessed on: 10/04/2019
- [6] World Bank. (2020). The Economic Impact of COVID-19 on South Asia. Available at: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/33478/9781464815669.pdf?sequence=5&isAllowed=y>; Accessed on: 13/05/20.
- [7] World Bank. (April, 2020). The Economy in the Time of COVID-19. America: World Bank. World Economy Outlook, April 2020, Available at: <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/Issues/2020/04/14/weo-april-2020>; Accessed on: 21/06/20